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**MARKETING PROBLEMS AND OPPORTUNITIES TO SOLVE THEM IN OILCROP
PRODUCING ENTERPRISES**

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Annotation. *This in the article oily crops grower marketing problems in enterprises illuminated . Oily crops grower marketing problems in enterprises solution reach possibilities showing given*

Key words: *oily crops , oil crops grower enterprises , marketing, marketing problems .*

Introduction. An important condition for the successful development of oilseed-growing enterprises is the correct and efficient organization of production, efficient use of resources, planning and management. Marketing and its management is the most important component of organizing the process of increasing the sales volume of the company's product . In recent years, consumer preferences have changed and many changes have taken place in the oil industry, especially in marketing activities such as targeting the online market, market segmentation, etc. This is the study of marketing problems in oilseeds growing enterprises demand is enough

Study of the problem level. The marketing activities of oilseed enterprises are very different from other industries, because oil is one of the main resources that support people's lives. In addition, most of them require fast delivery, appropriate packaging.

"Other such as businesses The main goal of the economic activity of the oil-growing enterprises is to obtain maximum profit, for this it must ensure the competitiveness of the product, the possibility of changing and diversifying the assortment, which allows its effective, diversified and intensive development by introducing scientific and technical achievements into the enterprise's activity. gives" [1].

Any product has a life cycle of development and decline, market saturation. At the same time, the implementation of relevant marketing strategic activities, including the introduction of innovations, requires the provision of qualified personnel, which, in turn, requires the improvement of the qualifications of employees, and in some cases, even personnel changes. In addition, the management of the enterprise uses incentive mechanisms and retraining of employees, which motivates employees to increase labor productivity and self-sufficiency. Innovation in the marketing of oilseed enterprises includes both new types of products and modern ideas in the field of marketing, the use of modern methods of selling products, etc.

"In the context of market relations, strategic planning of enterprise activities focuses on new developments introduced into the industry and their development prospects, all of which require capital investments as well as the promotion of marketing policy, because the manufactured product must meet the current needs of the market. At the same time, today a policy is being conducted in the direction of reducing costs and increasing profitability, and for its implementation, existing problems and factors hindering the development of the enterprise should be identified. The increase in sales volume and

profitability is related to the loyalty of consumers, the period of purchase of this type of product and competitiveness" [2].

Quality assurance is a necessary condition in the process of introducing innovations to oilseed enterprises, as in many cases they are not taken into account in planning. When planning innovations in this area, it is very important to take into account the available space in the market, where "infiltration" is possible, and the issues of ensuring environmental and sanitary standards.

The Ansoff matrix can be effectively used in the development and implementation of innovations in the economic activity of the enterprise, marketing strategies. The next important issue is planning the product and market development strategy. This matrix is used in many enterprises in various industries, including oilseeds enterprises (table).

Table 1**Ansoff matrix [3]**

Markets	Products	
	extant	new
there is	come in to go strategy	the product work work out strategy
new	the market development strategy	diversification strategy

"When developing the market, you must first enter the existing sales areas, that is: the company already works in this market, has a reputation, has its own customers who are loyal to the product, where all marketing and advertising campaigns are aimed at existing customers. At the same time, the company increases its market share, expands and attracts new customers. Strategy can then be used to define product development, which means entering an existing market with innovation and attracting customers. The strategy of development of new markets implies entry into new trade areas where the enterprise is unknown, new consumers and new distribution channels are needed, new segmentation in the market and its development. With a diversification strategy, it is necessary to enter a new market with an innovative product, where there is no information about consumers and new marketing activities, involvement of financial and labor resources, new distribution channels and a high risk of failure." [3].

The above strategies can be widely used by local producers in the oilseeds production market of the republic, as well as in export to foreign countries.

Marketing and its management play an important role in order to increase the volume of sales and increase economic efficiency, and it is of social importance, it is the relevant study, research, analysis and development of a certain group of consumers and society as a whole. requires the maximum satisfaction of their needs for relevant products and services.

" The production-economic importance of marketing consists in increasing production efficiency, reducing the volume of unsold goods, and reducing production costs, taking into account the conditions related to product sales, production flexibility and innovation" [4].

It is also important to analyze the current and capital costs of production, based on which cost estimates are made and compared with related products of similar quality and volume. In this case, it is recommended to carry out calculations of the profitability of the assortment and costs, with their help it is possible to determine a number of products that do not justify the costs and production can be stopped, so that the maximum cost reduction ensures the maximum profit.

Research Methods

The research methods are based on studying, analyzing, and generalizing scientific research conducted by foreign economists. During the research process, dialectics, system approach, and system analysis methods were employed.

Analysis and Results

“There are various types of oilseed products, and their production holds social significance for the society. The high production costs and unsatisfactory profitability of some products are offset by producing other assortments” [4]. A vivid example of this can be seen in the production of oilseed products. According to international experience, companies use specialized software packages to identify unprofitable assortments, set effective and competitive prices, and so on.

To ensure the profitability of the produced product assortment, advertising activities are necessary, through which the product’s strengths, its importance, and necessity for the consumer are revealed.

“According to international practice, the 4P concept is applied. The 4P concept (marketing mix) is a marketing theory based on four fundamental ‘coordinates’ of marketing planning:

Product: product or service, assortment, quality, product features, design, and ergonomics;

Price: price, additional charges, discounts;

Promotion: promotion, advertising, sales promotion;

Place: distribution, placement locations, distribution channels, sales staff” [5].

The above concept ensures high efficiency in product sales by emphasizing: firstly, the importance of producing competitive products and focusing on safety and quality from a food perspective; secondly, forming prices that need to be competitive and ensure maximum profit; thirdly, promoting the product in the market - advertising, special offers, promotions, etc., to ensure effective implementation; and fourthly, the significant role of the regional location of retail outlets where products are sold.

Furthermore, the ASRR (*customer acquisition, customer service, customer retention, and customer return*) mechanism is also used, which involves attracting customers, working with them, retaining them, and ensuring their return. This mechanism would be applicable in oilseed-producing enterprises in our country.

Additionally, using SWOT analysis is crucial for determining the market condition, external competitive barriers and opportunities, internal strengths and weaknesses, ensuring market competitiveness and positioning.

“In oilseed-producing enterprises, consumer segmentation, which includes price and age segments according to centralization, residential areas, and purchasing advantages, plays an equally significant role in the success of product promotion. Segmentation helps determine pricing policies and ensures customer attraction and retention. It helps identify new markets and place products, promote distribution networks, and apply effective pricing marketing strategies that aid in product placement, advertising, and meeting consumer needs” [6].

A good example of applying a pricing marketing strategy in our country is the pricing policy conducted by some enterprises in the oilseed production sector, which segments consumers based on income, slightly differs from other producers, and ensures relatively higher quality. Currently, marketing management in

oilseed-producing enterprises is not adequately developed, indicating a lack of competitiveness of local products, especially in foreign trade. All these factors also hinder the development of competitiveness in the country's economy. However, it should be noted that in recent years, the marketing mechanism has been modernized, with the introduction of the latest technological solutions, financial management, and sales management systems. At the same time, selling oil products in our country is challenging due to the small market size and the large portion of the population being unable to pay. As a result, producers focus on quality and oil output indicators, with consumers demonstrating brand loyalty and attachment.

In oilseed-producing enterprises in our country, marketing management plays a crucial role due to competition, and producers periodically develop strategies and pricing policies for promoting products in the market, organizing sales points, and distribution processes.

“Research into the food market shows that for effective marketing, attention should be given to flexible pricing policies in product sales, assortment replacement, and structural changes in the sales process, as well as applying innovations in packaging considering the effectiveness of research and development processes, priority directions, market needs, and trends. Correct packaging and proper product display at retail points can increase sales volume, as buyers currently pay significant attention to packaging and its quality. Product utility and effectiveness should also be considered in pricing” [7].

“The process of selling oil products involves a complex mechanism, as it requires delivering the necessary quantity of goods to the right place at the appropriate price and within the required time to meet demand. Sellers create specific schedules for continuous delivery. The process of organizing sales also considers region, population size, purchasing power, and demand, which help determine and forecast the appropriate supply volumes” [3].

For exporting companies, having distribution networks is essential to increase sales effectiveness. To increase export volumes, it is important to conduct regular marketing campaigns in the countries where products are shipped, particularly promoting and advertising the brand through special showcases in trade outlets. Considering the competition in the market, periodic advertising videos showing the product manufacturing processes are also a good option.

Currently, paid advertising campaigns and promotions on social media are widely used, allowing high results with small investments. To increase sales volume and improve product image, oil product-exporting enterprises can follow the aforementioned examples and conduct paid advertising campaigns targeted at buyer communities in various cities or other countries where products are sold.

For promoting the brand and increasing sales volume, it is recommended to actively collaborate with legal entities, especially retail points, stores, and others, in a B2B (business-to-business) approach. Utilizing factors such as production prices and wholesale discounts is effective here.

Applying this experience in our country, for example in retail stores, ensures the delivery of a wide range of products based on contractual relationships and expands joint activities, including selling not only their products but also those of partner companies.

To ensure effective foreign sales of products, marketing functions, especially outsourcing market-specific roles, can be used. This involves transferring marketing organizational functions to a foreign country with better market knowledge. This facilitates B2B model collaboration and customer engagement.

Using outsourcing allows companies to expand their operations, increase production volume, and so on. It helps reduce costs, save resources, expand access to the latest technologies, identify new markets through segmentation, increase competitiveness, protect commercial secrets and rights, and develop partnerships.

Within outsourcing, scouting also plays a significant role - conducting scientific and technical research, which can lead to discovering the latest innovations and technological solutions even at the early stages of distribution in the oil industry. Based on this, new scientific-economic structures focused on implementing, developing innovative ideas, expanding assortments and sales volumes, implementing market mechanisms, increasing production costs and profitability, and reducing production volumes are being formed [8].

Our monitoring and observations show that, alongside local products, various oil products from Kazakhstan, the Russian Federation, and other countries are available in retail stores.

Currently, problems arise in organizing exports, especially when oil product producers face difficulties in establishing efficient production due to a lack of transport means, partners, and distribution networks in foreign markets.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Summarizing the marketing issues among oilseed-producing enterprises in our country, we can conclude that the capabilities and policies of our manufacturers do not allow them to respond to global changes, mainly related to financial investments.

The proposed recommendations and methods used in global practice include outsourcing marketing functions in the importing country, collaborating in sales and distribution, introducing new innovations, and advertising. Producers in our country should utilize these methods to increase sales volume and contribute to reducing oil product imports and increasing exports.

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